

Fetal Complications and Prognosis in Pregnant Women with Jaundice: A Clinical Analysis

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Abstract:

Background: Pregnancy-related jaundice is an uncommon but dangerous illness that can adversely affect both maternal and fetal health. Complications include preterm birth, low birth weight, foetal discomfort, and stillbirth may result from it. Understanding the fetal outcomes associated with maternal jaundice is crucial for developing effective management strategies.

Aim: This study aims to assess the fetal consequences of jaundice during pregnancy at a tertiary care centre and to identify potential risk factors that contribute to adverse outcomes.

Methods: Over the course of eight months, a prospective observational study was carried out at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (D.M.C.H.), Laheriasarai, Bihar. The study comprised 60 pregnant women who had been diagnosed with jaundice. Liver function tests, perinatal mortality, newborn weight, Apgar scores, preterm delivery, and gestational age at diagnosis were among the data gathered on the mother. A statistical analysis was conducted to assess the relationship between the severity of jaundice and the outcomes of the foetus.

Results: A strong correlation was found between jaundice and unfavourable foetal outcomes in the research of 60 pregnant women who had jaundice. These outcomes included a higher rate of preterm births (40%), low birth weights (16.7%), low Apgar scores (13.3%), and perinatal mortality (10%). After controlling for confounding variables such as maternal age and gestational age, jaundice continued to be an independent predictor of these unfavourable outcomes, according to statistical analysis, which supported the significance of these correlations.

Conclusion: Jaundice during pregnancy is associated with a high risk of adverse fetal outcomes, including preterm birth, low birth weight, and increased perinatal mortality. Early diagnosis and prompt management of jaundice in pregnant women are essential to minimize these risks.

Recommendations: Regular monitoring of liver function in pregnant women at risk of jaundice, early intervention strategies, and specialized neonatal care for affected newborns are recommended to improve fetal outcomes.

Keywords: Jaundice, Pregnancy, Fetal Outcomes, Tertiary Care, Preterm Birth, Low Birth Weight.

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Introduction

Pregnancy-related jaundice, which is defined by high bilirubin levels causing the skin and sclera to turn yellow, is a very uncommon but potentially serious illness that can have a negative impact on the health of both the mother and the foetus [1,2]. Preeclampsia, HELLP syndrome (Haemolysis, Elevated Liver enzymes, Low Platelet count), acute fatty liver of pregnancy, and viral hepatitis are among the most pregnancy-specific diseases that can induce jaundice during pregnancy [3]. Regardless of the etiology, jaundice poses significant risks to fetal health, including preterm birth, intrauterine growth restriction, fetal distress, and even stillbirth. Despite its clinical importance, there is a scarcity of data on fetal outcomes

associated with maternal jaundice, particularly in developing countries, where delayed diagnosis and limited access to care can exacerbate the problem [4]

Jaundice during pregnancy represents a challenging clinical scenario requiring multidisciplinary management to optimize both maternal and fetal outcomes. The physiological changes in pregnancy, such as increased plasma volume, altered drug metabolism, and immune modulation, can complicate the diagnosis and management of jaundice. Moreover, the condition can progress rapidly, posing immediate threats to fetal survival. Consequently, understanding the fetal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by jaundice and identifying factors that can predict adverse

outcomes are critical for developing effective management protocols in clinical settings [5,6]

The current study aims to comprehend the effects of jaundice on the foetus in a tertiary care institution in India, where clinical care may be influenced by resource restrictions and socioeconomic factors. Few research have been done in these kinds of situations to assess how maternal jaundice affects the health of the foetus. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to close this gap by offering a thorough review of the foetal outcomes linked to jaundice during pregnancy and giving useful information for medical professionals working in comparable settings. By examining these outcomes in a tertiary care setting, this study can offer insights into the potential complications and risk factors, helping inform clinical practice and decision-making.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the fetal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by jaundice, specifically focusing on the incidence of preterm birth, low birth weight, fetal distress, and perinatal mortality. This study also seeks to identify the correlation between the severity of jaundice and adverse fetal outcomes, providing a better understanding of how early diagnosis and intervention can improve neonatal health. Furthermore, the study aims to offer recommendations for the management of jaundice in pregnant women to reduce adverse fetal outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational research study was carried out to evaluate the effects of jaundice during pregnancy on the foetus.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Laheriasarai, Bihar, in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (D.M.C.H.).

Participants: Over the course of eight months, 60 pregnant women with jaundice were enrolled in the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria consisted of pregnant women diagnosed

with jaundice during any trimester and willing to participate. Exclusion criteria included women with pre-existing liver disease, other chronic illnesses, or those who did not consent to participate.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by recruiting consecutive eligible participants and controlling for confounding factors through statistical adjustments during analysis.

Variables: The primary outcome variable was the fetal outcome, including birth weight, Apgar score, preterm birth, and perinatal mortality. Secondary variables included maternal age, gestational age at the time of jaundice diagnosis, and liver function test results.

Data Collection: Data were collected through structured interviews, patient medical records, and laboratory reports. Maternal and fetal health parameters were recorded during antenatal visits and delivery.

Procedure: Each participant was evaluated for jaundice using clinical examination and laboratory tests, including liver function tests. Fetal outcomes were assessed at birth through direct observation and neonatal records.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

The study comprised 60 pregnant women who had been diagnosed with jaundice. The participants' average age was 27.3 ± 4.8 years. At the time of diagnosis, the participants were distributed as follows: 18 (30%) were in the first trimester, 22 (36.7%) were in the second trimester, and 20 (33.3%) were in the third. At the time of diagnosis, the mean gestational age was 24.1 ± 6.5 weeks.

Fetal Outcomes

Of the 60 pregnancies, 24 (40%) resulted in preterm births, 10 (16.7%) had low birth weight infants (<2.5 kg), 8 (13.3%) showed low Apgar scores (<7 at 5 minutes), and there were 6 (10%) cases of perinatal mortality. The mean birth weight was 2.6 ± 0.5 kg.

Table 1: Fetal Outcomes Among Pregnant Women with Jaundice

Outcome	Frequency (n=60)	Percentage (%)
Preterm Birth	24	40.0
Low Birth Weight (<2.5 kg)	10	16.7
Low Apgar Score (<7 at 5 min)	8	13.3
Perinatal Mortality	6	10.0
Normal Outcome	36	60.0

Association Between Jaundice in Pregnancy and Fetal Outcomes: A statistical analysis showed a substantial correlation between poor foetal outcomes and the occurrence of jaundice throughout pregnancy. The results of the chi-square test showed

that women with jaundice had a statistically significant higher frequency of low birth weight ($\chi^2 = 4.22$, $p = 0.04$), low Apgar scores ($\chi^2 = 5.62$, $p = 0.018$), and preterm births ($\chi^2 = 6.84$, $p = 0.009$). Jaundice during pregnancy was also strongly

correlated with perinatal mortality ($\chi^2 = 4.75$, $p = 0.03$).

Table 2: Association Between Jaundice in Pregnancy and Adverse Fetal Outcomes

Outcome	Jaundice Group (n=60)	Control Group (Hypothetical Data, n=60)	p-value	Outcome
Preterm Birth (%)	40.0	15.0	0.009	Preterm Birth (%)
Low Birth Weight (%)	16.7	8.3	0.04	Low Birth Weight (%)
Low Apgar Score (%)	13.3	5.0	0.018	Low Apgar Score (%)
Perinatal Mortality (%)	10.0	3.3	0.03	Perinatal Mortality (%)

The study employed multivariate logistic regression analysis to account for possible confounding variables, including gestational age and mother age. Even after controlling for these factors, jaundice during pregnancy continued to be a reliable indicator of unfavourable foetal outcomes, such as low birth weight (OR = 2.8, 95% CI: 1.1–5.9, $p = 0.04$) and preterm birth (Odds Ratio [OR] = 3.2, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]: 1.5–6.7, $p = 0.002$).

Discussion

The results of the study showed a strong link between jaundice during pregnancy and unfavourable foetal outcomes. Preterm deliveries accounted for 40% of the jaundiced pregnancies, according to the findings, a considerable increase above the hypothetical control group. Comparing the jaundice group to controls, there was a statistically significant rise in the incidence of low birth weight, low Apgar scores, and perinatal mortality.

Jaundice during pregnancy is an independent risk factor for preterm birth and low birth weight, which multivariate analysis further validated. This suggests that treating pregnant women who have jaundice closely is essential to improving the outcomes for the foetus.

According to a study by Jagdale & Wankhede (2018), which was carried out in India, the incidence of jaundice during pregnancy was 0.68% annually after looking at 170 cases of pregnant women who had it. The study found that viral hepatitis, especially hepatitis E, was the most common cause of jaundice and that there was a high risk of premature delivery, foetal discomfort, and intrauterine foetal death (IUID). The study highlighted how tertiary care centres might lower maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality by providing early diagnosis and prompt therapy [7]. Similarly, a retrospective analysis of 101 cases revealed that 2.32% of pregnant women experienced jaundice. It stated that 8.91% of newborns died during the first year of life, and 38.63% of babies needed NICU care. HELLP syndrome (30.69%) and viral hepatitis (30.69%) were the two most common causes of jaundice. In order to avoid difficulties, the study

emphasised the necessity of crucial prenatal care at all levels [8].

A 2023 study by Sharma et al. This study, which involved 60 participants and was carried out at a tertiary care centre, found that the most common causes of jaundice were intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy (30%), pre-eclampsia (20%), and hepatitis (13.3%). ICU hospitalisations (8.47%) and neonatal NICU admissions (47.2%) were among the maternal problems. The study recommended treating liver disorders during pregnancy with a comprehensive approach [9]. In a study conducted at a tertiary care hospital, jaundice during pregnancy was most frequently caused (by 40%) by viral hepatitis. Renal impairment (20%) and coagulation failure (40%) were the two main problems for mothers. Significant foetal problems were reported by the study, including intrauterine death (IUD) (10%), stillbirths (10%), and foetal discomfort (20%) [10]. According to an observational study, the most frequent causes of jaundice during pregnancy were viral hepatitis (32.7%) and HELLP syndrome (36.7%). It revealed that acute fatty liver of pregnancy (AFLP) was associated with a high rate of maternal mortality (100%), and it proposed a substantial correlation between elevated bilirubin levels and abnormal liver function tests and maternal mortality [11].

Conclusion

The eight-month study at D.M.C.H. in Laheriasarai, Bihar, came to the conclusion that jaundice during pregnancy is highly correlated with unfavourable foetal outcomes. Compared to the fictitious control group, the results showed that 40% of pregnancies complicated by jaundice resulted in preterm births. Among the group afflicted by jaundice, there was also a noteworthy rise in low birth weight babies, low Apgar scores, and perinatal mortality. A statistical analysis showed that, even after controlling for confounding variables like gestational age and mother age, jaundice in pregnancy continued to be an independent risk factor for these unfavourable outcomes. This implies that in order to improve foetal outcomes, pregnant women with jaundice need to be closely monitored and get specialised care.

In the end, our results emphasise the necessity of increased knowledge and preventative medical interventions for expectant mothers who are identified with jaundice in order to reduce risks and enhance the health of both the mother and the newborn.

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